

Space anemia unexplained: red blood cells seem to be space-proof

Giampaolo Minetti^{1*}, Anna Yu. Bogdanova², Heimo Mairbäurl³, Lars Kaestner^{4,5}

1. Department of Biology and Biotechnology “L. Spallanzani”, Laboratories of Biochemistry, University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy.
2. ²Red Blood Cell Research Group, Institute of Veterinary Physiology, University of Zürich, Zürich, Switzerland.
3. ³Translational Pneumology, University Hospital Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany.
4. ⁴Experimental Physics, Dynamics of Fluids Group, Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany.
5. ⁵Theoretical Medicine and Biosciences, Campus University Hospital, Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany.

*Correspondence

Giampaolo Minetti, University of Pavia, Pavia, Department of Biology and Biotechnology “L. Spallanzani”, Laboratories of Biochemistry, Via Agostino Bassi, 21 – 27100 Pavia, Italy.
Phone: +39 0382 987891. Email: minetti@unipv.it

Abstract

It is with great interest that we read the report by Trudel et al. (Nat. Med. **28**, 59-62, 2022), who propose that accelerated hemolysis significantly contributes to “space anemia”. The authors have monitored hematological parameters and exhaled carbon monoxide (CO) in astronauts during 5 months-long space missions on the ISS, and up to one year after return. They observed an average 11% decrease in hemoglobin concentration between pre- and post-mission values, and a >50% increase in the rate of CO elimination by crewmembers onboard the ISS, which was ascribed to accelerated extravascular hemolysis of red blood cells. However, their interpretation is not consistent with the data. Furthermore, we challenge the term “anemia” because Hb was at most decreased to low-normal. We propose here alternative explanations for the elevation of exhaled CO, which, of course, require experimental proof. Despite this, we value the sophisticated experimental approach in clarifying hematological changes during a prolonged stay in space, which go beyond neocytolysis and other concepts attempting to explain “space anemia”.

The steady-state red blood cell (RBC) number is regulated by the rate of RBC production, under control of hypoxia inducible factor (HIF)-2 α and erythropoietin (EPO), whereas their clearance rate appears to be constant, reflecting the removal of senescent RBCs mainly (Beutler, 2001). It is still debated whether the reduction in total RBCs observed during space missions, or upon return to sea level from high altitude adaptation, or in chronic kidney patients after terminating an EPO-therapy, might occur faster than expected because of accelerated clearance, added to decreased production of RBCs at sub-normal EPO plasma levels. According to the neocytolysis hypothesis, when EPO levels drop young RBCs are destroyed at the same time that senescent RBCs continue disappearing at their normal rate, resulting in an accelerated clearance (Risso et al., 2014; Alfrey et al., 1997). This hypothesis gained credit as a possible explanation of “space anemia” as one of the many health risks associated with space missions (Alfrey et al., 1996). Neocytolysis has recently been falsified in the case of return from high altitude (Klein et al., 2021; Recktenwald et al., 2021).

Under basal conditions, a healthy adult expires ≈ 0.43 ml/h of endogenously produced carbon monoxide (CO), corresponding to $\approx 1.92 \times 10^{-5}$ mol/h of catabolized heme, resulting in equal amounts of CO, Fe and biliverdin (bilirubin) (Coburn, 2012). Approximately 75% to 85% of eliminated CO originates from breakdown of hemoglobin (Hb) heme, the remainder from liver hemoproteins (Abraham et al., 1996; Schacter, 1988). Thus, $\approx 1.54 \times 10^{-5}$ mol/h is the rate of CO elimination derived from Hb, corresponding to ≈ 5.9 g Hb per day, i.e. $\approx 0.8\%$ of the total Hb of an adult with a blood Hb concentration [Hb] of 14.5 g/dl and a total blood volume of 5 liters. This number is consistent with the clearance rate of normal human RBCs, which survive 120 days and are eliminated on a strictly time-dependent basis with minimal random destruction: in this steady state, the same number of reticulocytes enters the circulation every day. Deviations from this regimen are only known for hemolytic anemia conditions, where RBCs turn over faster, due to an increase in random clearance, which is compensated by accelerated erythropoiesis only partially (hence the anemia) (Beutler, 2001). In these conditions, the rate of Hb catabolism, as reflected by the levels of exhaled CO, can become one order of magnitude higher than normal (Coburn, 2012).

Trudel et al. (2022) measured [Hb] in the crewmembers on two occasions only, 8 months apart from each other: 3 months before launch (median [Hb] = 14.3 g/dl), and 4 days after landing (12.7 g/dl), which is 5 months after arrival on the ISS (Trudel et al., 2022). The difference of 1.6 g/dl, corresponding to an 11% decrease from baseline, is a small change and no valid proof of increased hemolysis, nor a sign of anemia. Moreover, any imbalance in RBC turnover can only be appreciated by measuring total Hb mass, not [Hb], which is subject to fluctuations in plasma volume that occur upon entering microgravity and on return (Alfrey et al., 1996; Udden et al., 1995).

Nevertheless, let us discuss how the authors correlated the CO elimination data with the extent of hemolysis. Based on previous data (Shahin et al., 2020) the rate of CO elimination in space was, on average, $\approx 2.59 \times 10^{-5}$ mol/h, persisting for 5 months on the ISS. This corresponds to a $>50\%$ increase with respect to pre-mission values, and to ≈ 9.7 g of Hb per day of the 157 days at the ISS. Even assuming that erythropoiesis continued at the normal pace, corresponding to ≈ 6 g Hb daily (which is unlikely, as EPO levels dropped below basal and stayed low for a few weeks after arrival at the ISS), at the end of the 5-month mission each crew member would end up with a [Hb] of < 2 g/dl.

It may be argued that a parallel increase in erythropoietic rate could have compensated for the accelerated hemolysis, because EPO levels were 16% higher than basal in the second half of the mission. However, all the surrogate parameters of erythrokinetics (elevated plasma iron: ferritin, saturated transferrin), and previous published results (Alfrey et al., 1996; Udden et al., 1995), would exclude this possibility. Thus, the sustained elevation of exhaled CO (Trudel et al., 2022) is clearly incompatible with the relatively mild decrease in [Hb] observed in astronauts at the end of their mission, but is compatible with alternative explanations as proposed below.

Early studies showed that the amounts of eliminated CO were always larger than expected from plasma bilirubin levels (Abraham et al., 1996; Schacter, 1988). This is because bilirubin derived from catabolism of liver hemoproteins is not secreted into plasma but directly excreted into the gallbladder, whereas bilirubin derived from extravascular hemolysis of RBCs appears in plasma, to be delivered and processed further in the liver. In both cases, CO is mainly eliminated with the expired air. An increased extravascular hemolysis should therefore correspond to increased levels of plasma bilirubin, which did not occur in the astronauts (**Figure 1**). Elevated CO elimination and extravascular hemolysis might be also explained, at least partially, by ineffective erythropoiesis (White et al., 1967) because of low EPO levels. In this case, CO release would be derived from breakdown of precursors in the bone marrow, not from circulating RBCs. The lack of decrease in haptoglobin supports this notion (Trudel et al., 2022).

However, the actual increase in haptoglobin, that was left unmentioned in the report by Trudel et al. (2022) (**Figure 1**), is unexpected and its source needs to be identified.

As an alternative to accelerated hemolysis, the excess CO elimination is more plausibly explained by stimulated catabolism of liver hemoproteins, among which the short-lived cytochrome P-450 accounts for 70% of heme synthesized in the liver (Schacter, 1988). The gene encoding the inducible isoform of heme oxygenase (HO-1), most abundant in spleen and liver (Abraham et al., 1996), appears to be activated by a far greater variety of factors than any other gene (Maines and Gibbs, 2005). It is not known if its expression is stimulated in space. Another contributor to CO elimination might be breakdown of myoglobin heme, which has never been measured in space.

The supplementary tables (Trudel et al., 2022) contain additional interesting information not discussed, showing that most of the increase in expired CO resulted from males, whereas there was no increase from female astronauts, indicating a strong sex difference. Moreover, plasma bilirubin changed in males and females, but into opposite directions, resulting in no change when values were averaged (**Figure 1**). This dimorphism certainly requires further investigation.

In summary, elevated liver-heme turnover, apoptotic destruction of erythroid precursors in the bone marrow due to lack of EPO, a physiological rate of RBC clearance and sex differences, could also explain Trudel et al. results. These changes appear not necessarily causally related with accelerated hemolysis. Not contradictory to this statement, their work presents an interesting data set that allows numerous unique interpretations and fosters new research in space medicine.

Figure 1: Graphical visualization of hemolysis-related parameters, normalized to pre-flight values. The data are taken from the Supplemental Table 1 of Trudel et al. 2022.¹ Data do not support occurrence of hemolysis because bilirubin did not change early in the ISS and later even decreased (one would expect an increase), and haptoglobin increased (decreased haptoglobin levels would indicate intravascular hemolysis). Furthermore, the transferrin saturation early after arrival in the ISS does not support stimulated erythropoiesis compensating for an initial loss of RBCs. Changes in parameters of iron metabolism might also be the consequence of different diets in space and on earth.

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